

PHILIPPINE PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS FOR TEACHERS-BASED TEACHERS PERFORMANCE AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED TEACHING-LEARNING DELIVERY

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ABSATRACT

This study focused in the descriptive and correlational analysis of Philippine Professional Standards for Teacher-Based Teachers performance and the students' academic performance as a basis in enhance teaching-learning delivery. The respondents of the study were composed of Grade five learners of Pahinga Norte Elementary School with a range of 10-13 years old. In order to gather the data, form the respondents, the researcher used the survey questionnaire. It is centered to test the relationship of the PPST-based teachers' performance in new normal towards the students' academic achievement in English, Science and Mathematics. Moreover, the gathered data shows that in the domain of content knowledge and pedagogy, learners perceived that they observed the indicators "frequently" among their teachers with the mean of 4.26. In the domain of learning environment, learners perceived that they observed the indicators "frequently" among their teachers with the mean of 4.34. In the domains of diversity of learners and assessment and reporting, learners shows that they observed the indicators "frequently" among their teachers with the mean of 4.20. In the domain of curriculum and planning, learners perceived that they observed the indicators "frequently" among their teachers with the mean of 4.29. In the domain of community linkages And Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development, learners shows that they observed the indicators "frequently" among their teachers with the mean of 4.29. In terms of academic achievement, 70% of the learners' performance in English lies in a satisfactory to outstanding level, while the 30% of them, lies in fairly satisfactory level. On the other hand, in science subject, 67.5% of the learners registers the satisfactory to outstanding level of performance while the remaining 32.5% of them lies in a fairly satisfactory level. Lastly, in the mathematics subject, 45% of the learners shows the very satisfactory to outstanding level of performance while the 55% of them registers fairly satisfactory to satisfactory level of performance. To narrow down the result, there is a positive significant relationship between the PPST-based teachers' performance and the student's academic achievement of in English, Science and Mathematics.

Keywords: Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, academic achievement